

Dyes Derived from 3-Methyl- Δ^4 -tetrahydrophthalic and 4-Methyl- Δ^4 -tetrahydrophthalic Acids. Part II. Effect of Introducing a Methyl Group at Different Positions (3 or 4) and also of Decreasing Unsaturation in the Phthalic Acid Portion of Phthalein Dyes

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3-Methyl- Δ^4 -tetrahydrophthalic and 4-methyl- Δ^4 -tetrahydrophthalic acids in the form of their anhydrides have been condensed with a number of aromatic hydroxy (phenols) and hydroxyamino (*m*-diethylaminophenol) compounds. The phthalein and rhodamine type of compounds, thus obtained, have been studied analytically and spectrophotometrically and compared with similar compounds obtained from phthalic acid. The resorcinol compounds have also been brominated and acetylated. The effect of introducing a methyl group at position 3 or 4 and also of decreasing unsaturation in the phthalic acid portion of phthaleins has been observed.

3-Methyl- Δ^4 -tetrahydrophthalic anhydride (I) and 4-methyl- Δ^4 -tetrahydrophthalic anhydride (II) have been condensed with phenol, resorcinol, orcinol, phloroglucinol, *o*-cresol, and *m*-diethylaminophenol under different conditions. The phthalein and rhodamine type of dyes obtained have been purified and analysed. The resorcinol compounds have been brominated and acetylated. The phenol, resorcinol, orcinol, phloroglucinol, *o*-cresol, *m*-diethylaminophenol, and tetrabromoresorcinol phthaleins have been studied spectrophotometrically. The absorption maxima obtained have been compared with those of phthaleins and rhodamines obtained from phthalic anhydride and the results discussed.

(I)

(II)

The phthaleins and rhodamines obtained are of the following types:

Type 1(a) from anhydride (I).

Type 1(b) from anhydride (II).

- IIIa and IIIb : $R^1 = R^2 = R^4 = H$; $R^3 = OH$.
 IVa and IVb : $R^1 = -CH_3$; $R^2 = R^4 = H$; $R^3 = OH$.
 Va and Vb : $R^1 = R^3 = OH$; $R^2 = R^4 = H$.
 VIa and VIb : $R^1 = R^2 = R^4 = H$; $R^3 = N(C_2H_5)_2$.
 VIIa and VIIb : $R^1 = H$; $R^2 = R^4 = -Br$; $R^3 = OH$.
 VIIIa and VIIIb : $R^1 = R^2 = R^4 = H$; $R^3 = OCOCH_3$.

Type 2(a) from anhydride (I).

Type 2(b) from anhydride (II).

- IXa and IXb : $R^1 = OH$; $R^2 = H$.
 Xa and Xb : $R^1 = OH$; $R^2 = CH_3$.

EXPERIMENTAL

trans-Piperylene, b. p. 41-42° (B.D.H.) was condensed with maleic anhydride to obtain 3-methyl- Δ^4 -tetrahydrophthalic anhydride¹ (I). Similarly isoprene, b. p. 35-36° (B.D.H.) was condensed with maleic anhydride to afford 4-methyl- Δ^4 -tetrahydrophthalic anhydride² (II). The products (I) and (II) were crystallised from light petroleum (40-60°).

1. Craig, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1943, **65**, 1006; Farmer and Warren, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1931, 3234.

2. Farmer and Warren, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1931, 3221, 3234.

These melted at 61° (acid, m.p. 150-153°) and 63° (acid, m.p. 155°) respectively. The anhydrides (I) and (II) were then used for the preparation of phthaleins and rhodamines given below.

Resorcinol-3-methyl- Δ^4 -tetrahydrophthalein (IIIa).—The anhydride (I) (1.66 g.) and resorcinol (2.2 g.) were intimately mixed and heated to 160° in an oil bath. A few drops of H₂SO₄ (conc., 3-4) were added and the temperature was raised to 180° and maintained for 3 hours to complete the reaction. The hard product after cooling was extracted with dilute NaOH solution and filtered. The phthalein was then precipitated by adding HCl (dil.) in small portions to the alkaline filtrate. The crude phthalein was purified by a second precipitation followed by crystallisation from ethanol. The brick-red crystals thus obtained were finally dried at 110° in an electric oven.

Resorcinol-4-methyl- Δ^4 -tetrahydrophthalein (IIIb).—The anhydride (II) (1.66 g.) and resorcinol (2.2 g.) were condensed and the phthalein was obtained in the same way as the resorcinol compound (IIIa).

Orcinol-3-methyl- Δ^4 -tetrahydrophthalein (IVa).—An intimate mixture of anhydride (I) (1.66 g.) and orcinol (2.48 g.) was heated at 140-50° for 4 hours in presence of H₂SO₄ (conc., 3-4 drops) as condensing agent. The hard product was powdered and extracted with dilute NaOH solution. The phthalein was precipitated and purified like resorcinol compound (IIIa).

Orcinol-4-methyl- Δ^4 -tetrahydrophthalein (IVb).—The anhydride (II) (1.66 g.) and orcinol (2.48 g.) were heated in an oil bath at 115° to 120° for 5 hours in presence of H₂SO₄ (conc., 3-4 drops). The phthalein was obtained from the condensation product as in the orcinol compound (IVa).

Phloroglucinol-3-methyl- Δ^4 -tetrahydrophthalein (Va).—The anhydride (I) (1.66 g.) was intimately mixed with phloroglucinol (2.52 g.) and heated to 180-200° in an oil bath for 4 hours in presence of H₂SO₄ (conc., 3-4 drops). The phthalein was extracted, precipitated, and purified like the resorcinol compound (IIIa).

Phloroglucinol-4-methyl- Δ^4 -tetrahydrophthalein (Vb).—An intimate mixture of the anhydride (II) (1.66 g.) and phloroglucinol (2.52 g.) was condensed, extracted, precipitated, and purified like the phloroglucinol compound (Va).

m-Diethylaminophenol-3-methyl- Δ^4 -tetrahydrophthalein (VIa).—The anhydride (I) (1.66 g.) and *m*-diethylaminophenol (2.82 g.) were heated at 110° to 115° for about 5 hours in presence of H₂SO₄ (conc.). The condensation product was powdered and extracted with HCl (dil.) and filtered. The rhodamine was precipitated by adding dilute NaOH solution to the acidic filtrate. The dye was further purified by a second precipitation followed by crystallisation from ethanol. It was dried at 100° in an electric oven.

m-Diethylaminophenol-4-methyl- Δ^4 -tetrahydrophthalein (VIb).—An intimate mixture of the anhydride (II) (1.66 g.) and *m*-diethylaminophenol (2.82 g.) was condensed (110–115°), extracted, and purified like the compound (VIa).

Tetrabromoresorcinol-3-methyl- Δ^4 -tetrahydrophthalein (VIIa) was obtained by brominating (IIIa), using the method of Baeyer³.

Tetrabromoresorcinol-4-methyl- Δ^4 -tetrahydrophthalein (VIIb) was obtained by bromination of (IIIb) like the compound (VIIa).

Resorcinol-3-methyl- Δ^4 -tetrahydrophthalein diacetate (VIIIa) was obtained by acetylating the resorcinol compound (IIIa) with acetic anhydride in presence of fused sodium acetate and purified by crystallisation from ethanol.

Resorcinol-4-methyl- Δ^4 -tetrahydrophthalein diacetate (VIIIb) was obtained like compound (VIIIa).

Phenol-3-methyl- Δ^4 -tetrahydrophthalein (IXa).—A mixture of the anhydride (I) (1.66 g.) and phenol (3 g.) was heated at 110–115° for about 14 hours in presence of H₂SO₄ (conc., 8 drops) as condensing agent. The black semisolid mass thus obtained was transferred to a flask containing 50 ml of water and the excess of phenol removed in a current of steam. The crude solid residue was extracted with very dilute NaOH and the phthalein was precipitated with dilute HCl. The compound was partly decolorised with animal charcoal and crystallised from EtOH-H₂O (2:1).

Phenol-4-methyl- Δ^4 -tetrahydrophthalein (IXb).—The anhydride (I) (1.66 g.) and phenol (3 g.) were condensed, extracted, precipitated and purified like the phenolic compound (IXa).

o-Cresol-3-methyl- Δ^4 -tetrahydrophthalein (Xa).—A mixture of the anhydride (I) (1.66 g.) and *o*-cresol (3 g.) was heated at 110° to 115° for about 14 hours in presence of H₂SO₄ (conc., 8 drops) as condensing agent. The phthalein was separated and purified in the same way as (IXa).

o-Cresol-4-methyl- Δ^4 -tetrahydrophthalein (Xb).—The anhydride (II) (1.66 g.) was condensed with *o*-cresol (3.5 g.) and the phthalein obtained as in compound (Xa).

Melting points, analyses, crystalline appearance, colour in ethanol, and change in colour on addition of alkali, etc. are shown in Table I.

The absorption maxima ($\lambda_{\max}$) of the compounds (Tables II & III) prepared were determined using 'Hilger Uvispek' spectrophotometer. The maxima for phthalein type of compounds were taken in ethanolic solution containing a drop of 5% NaOH and the maxima for the rhodamine type of compounds were determined in the same solvent containing a drop of 5*N*-HCl. The maxima for phthaleins and rhodamines from phthalic anhydride were also determined under similar conditions.

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TABLE I

Compound No.	**M.P.	Appearance.	*Colour in EtOH.	Formula.	Found.	Reqd.
IIIa	220°	Brick-red	Brown-red (Reddish pink [†])	C ₂₁ H ₁₈ O ₅	C : 71.50% H : 5.20	72.00% 5.14
IIIb	240°	Reddish brown	Reddish brown (Reddish pink [†])	"	C : 71.75 H : 5.00	72.00 5.14
IVa	160-65°	Dark-red	Yellow (Orange-red [†])	C ₂₃ H ₂₂ O ₅	C : 73.10 H : 5.80	73.01 5.82
IVb	135°	"	Yellow (Orange-green)	"	C : 72.90 H : 5.86	73.01 5.82
Va	> 290°	Orange-red	Yellow (Orange-red)	C ₂₁ H ₁₈ O ₇	C : 66.00 H : 4.75	65.97 4.71
Vb	260°	"	Yellow-Orange (Orange-red)	"	C : 65.99 H : 4.75	65.97 4.71
VIa	120°	Dark pink	Deep pink (intensified with HCl)	C ₂₉ H ₃₆ O ₃ N ₂	C : 75.85 H : 7.83 N : 6.00	75.65 7.83 6.09
VIb	147°	Red	Pink (intensified with HCl)	"	C : 75.70 H : 7.90 N : 6.10	75.65 7.83 6.09
VIIa	> 300°	Dark red	Brick-red (Deep pink)	C ₂₁ H ₁₄ O ₅ Br ₄	Br : 47.90	48.05
VIIb	"	Brick-red	Brick-red, (")	"	Br : 47.80	48.05
VIIIa	145°	Brown	—	C ₂₅ H ₂₂ O ₇	C : 69.90 H : 5.10	69.12 5.07
VIIIb	155°	Yellow-brown	—	"	C : 68.85 H : 5.12	69.13 5.07
IXa	125°	Pinkish white powder	Yellowish brown (Pink)	C ₂₁ H ₂₀ O ₄	C : 74.90 H : 6.09	75.00 5.95
IXb	147°	Brownish white powder	Do	"	C : 75.10 H : 5.99	75.00 5.95
Xa	150°	Pinkish white powder	Reddish brown (Purple pink)	C ₂₃ H ₂₄ O ₄	C : 75.50 H : 6.60	75.82 6.59
Xb	"	"	Brown (Purple pink)	"	C : 75.40 H : 6.61	75.82 6.59

**Melts with decomposition.

*Change in colour with alkali or acid shown in parentheses.

†With green fluorescence.

TABLE II

Phenols.	Phthaleins.		Tetrahydrophthaleins.	
			3-Methyl- Δ^4	4-Methyl- Δ^4
Resorcinol	490 m μ ²	(Fluorescein)	485 m μ	495 m μ
Orcinol	490	(Orcein)	505	505
Phenol	545	(Phenolphthalein)	540	540
Phloroglucinol	460		460	460
o-Cresol	560		540	540
Tetrabromo- resorcinol	515	(Eosin)	515	515

TABLE III

From phthalic anhydride,	From 3-methyl- Δ^4 -tetrahydrophthalic anhydride.	From 4-methyl- Δ^4 -tetrahydrophthalic anhydride.
<i>m</i> -Diethylaminophenolphthalein (Rhodamine B)	<i>m</i> -Diethylaminophenol-3-methyl- Δ^4 -tetrahydrophthalein	<i>m</i> -Diethylaminophenol-4-methyl- Δ^4 -tetrahydrophthalein
545 m μ	545 m μ	545 m μ

DISCUSSION

A comparative study of the absorption maxima (λ_{max}) of the dyestuffs (phthaleins and rhodamines) shows that the changes in the lower portion of the phthalein dyes (introduction of one methyl group at position 3 or 4 and of decreasing unsaturation in the phthalic acid portion) have no appreciable effect on the light absorption, except in cases of *o*-cresol and orcinol and to some extent in the case of resorcinol compounds. In cases of *o*-cresol compounds of the anhydrides (I) and (II) the maximum absorption takes place at 540 m μ as compared with *o*-cresol phthalein, which absorbs at 560 m μ . whereas in the case of compounds of the anhydrides (I) and (II) the maximum absorption takes place at 505 m μ compared with orcinol phthalein (orcein) which absorbs at 490 m μ .

These slight variations may be due to the introduction of a methyl group and/or to the decreasing unsaturation in the phthalic acid portion. This is not consistent, however, with the other phenolic compounds which show the maximum absorption at the same wave length as the phthaleins from phthalic anhydride. These variations can only be accounted for if correct correlation between electronic oscillations and atomic vibrations is established.

The introduction of a methyl group at position 3 in the phthalic acid portion along with the decreasing unsaturation has something to do with the colour intensity of solutions because it has been observed that the dyes prepared from anhydride (I) show deeper colours in solution as compared with the dyes prepared from anhydride (II) (methyl group at position 4). But when compared with the dyes obtained from phthalic anhydride, the compounds of anhydrides (I) and (II) show a lower colour intensity in solutions of equal strength.

The authors express their sincere thanks to Dr. S. M. Mitra, Principal, Birla College and to Dr. R. D. Gupta, Head of the Department of Chemistry, Birla College, Pilani, for providing the necessary facilities.

One of the authors (N. C. Jain) also expresses his gratitude to the Government of India for granting him a research fellowship.